

Valid Publication of the Name *Opuntia polyacantha* var. *rhodantha* (Cactaceae)

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Abstract—Valid publication of the name *Opuntia polyacantha* var. *rhodantha*.

The widely used name *Opuntia polyacantha* var. *rhodantha* was never validly published. It is proposed here:

***Opuntia polyacantha* var. *rhodantha* (K.Schum.) M.van der Meer stat. nov.**

≡ *Opuntia rhodantha* K.Schum.

—Monatsschr. Kakteenk. vi. 111 (1896);

Rehnelt in Gartenwelt, i. 83 (1896);

K.Schum. Gesamtb. Kakt. 735 (1898);

Croizat in Cact. & Succ. Journ. Amer. xvi. 88 (1944)

Literature

Opuntia polyacantha, cold-hardy prickly pear cactus. Opuntia Web. (2020). Retrieved 22 May 2020, from <https://www.opuntiads.com/opuntia-polyacantha/>.

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